

Syntheses, characterizations and crystal structures of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with a tridentate Schiff base

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Abstract : One mononuclear nickel(II) complex [Ni(L)NCS] (1) and one dinuclear copper(II) complex [CuL(C₂O₄)CuL] (2), where HL = 2-(2-(dimethylamino)ethyliminomethyl)phenol) is a tridentate N₂O donor Schiff base, have been prepared and characterized. Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies have confirmed their structures. Complex 1 crystallizes in monoclinic space group *P*2₁/*c* with *a* = 13.886(4), *b* = 15.411(5), *c* = 32.907(10), β = 90.183(7) and complex 2 crystallizes in monoclinic space group *C*2 with *a* = 18.846(2), *b* = 10.954(2), *c* = 10.632(1), β = 119.837(8). Nickel(II) adopts a square planar geometry in 1; copper(II) exhibits a distorted square pyramidal geometry (Addison parameter (τ) = 0.116) in 2. The copper(II)-copper(II) distance in the asymmetric unit is 5.495 Å in complex 2. Complex 2 shows di- μ (O,O') *syn-syn* carboxylate bridging.

Keywords : Nickel(II), copper(II), tridentate Schiff base, thiocyanate, oxalate, crystal structures.

Introduction

The Schiff bases, formed by the condensation of an amine with a carbonyl compound¹, are very useful complexes for the inorganic chemists as these are widely used in designing molecular ferromagnets, in catalysis, in biological modeling applications, as liquid crystals and in heterogeneous catalysis² and also in self-assembling cluster complexes³. Schiff base complexes have also attracted the attention of physicists and chemists owing to their large NLO (non-linear optical) responses that are known since 1940s⁴. These complexes are characterized by exceptionally high stability constants comparable to those of biological receptors making them promising candidates for successful applications in the field of optoelectronic technologies⁵. Encouragement particularly for the syntheses of the Schiff bases complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II) for the study of their physical and chemical properties is provided by their strong role in bioinorganic chemistry and redox enzyme systems⁶, and may offer the basis of models for active sites of biological systems⁷ or act as catalysts⁸. Definitely the salen type Schiff bases, prepared from the condensation of a diamine with salicylaldehyde or its derivatives, are receiving the most attention among all the Schiff bases, because of the ability of

the phenoxo oxygen atoms to form μ_2 -bridges, thus affording high-nuclearity complexes⁹⁻¹¹, which could act as promising candidates to offer valuable insight into various natural electron-transfer events¹². N₂O donor tridentate Schiff bases can also easily be prepared on refluxing *N*-substituted diamine with salicylaldehyde or 3-methoxy salicylaldehyde^{13,14}. The ligands can then be used to form complexes with several transition metals¹⁵⁻¹⁷. We have used a N₂O donor Schiff base, *N,N'*-diethylethylene-*N*-3-methoxysalicylideneimine, in the present work to prepare copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes. Herein, we report the synthesis, structural features, spectroscopic characterization and X-ray crystal structures of a new complex of nickel(II), [Ni(L)NCS] and a new complex of copper(II), [CuL(C₂O₄)CuL].

Experimental

All starting materials were commercially available, reagent grade, and used as purchased without further purification.

Preparations :

Preparation of the ligand, HL (N,N'-diethylethylene-N-3-methoxysalicylideneimine) :

The tridentate Schiff base ligand, HL, was synthe-

sized by refluxing the *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine (10 mmol, 1.06 g) with 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde (20 mmol, 3.04 g) in methanol solution (20 ml) for *ca.* 1 h. The ligand was not isolated. The methanol solution of ligand was used for the synthesis of the complexes.

Synthesis of complex [Ni(L)NCS] (1) :

The methanol solution of nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (1 mmol, 0.238 g) was added to the ligand solution of HL (1 mmol, 0.250 g) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 1 h. To it, a methanol solution of NH_4SCN (1 mmol, 0.076 g) was added dropwise with continuous stirring for half an hour and the resulting solution was filtered. Single crystals of complex (1) suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained from the mother liquor.

Yield : 0.27 g (74%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{NiO}_2\text{S}$ (366.11) : C, 49.21; H, 5.78; N, 11.48. Found : C, 49.1; H, 5.6; N, 11.4%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S})$ 2110, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1620, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ 2921; UV-Vis spectrum, λ_{max} (nm), $[\epsilon_{\text{max}} (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1})]$ (acetonitrile), 332 (4657), 465 (472); magnetic moment : diamagnetic.

Synthesis of complex [(CuL)₂C₂O₄] (2) :

The methanol solution of copper(II) acetate monohydrate (1 mmol, 0.365 g) was added to the ligand solution of HL (1 mmol, 0.250 g) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 1 h. To it, a water solution of $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ (0.5 mmol, 0.076 g) was added dropwise with continuous stirring for 30 min and the green crystalline solid was separated by filtration. Single crystals of the complex (2), suitable for X-ray diffraction, were obtained from the acetonitrile solution.

Yield : 0.27 g (51%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{42}\text{Cu}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_8$ (713.78) : C, 50.48; H, 5.93; N, 7.85. Found : C, 50.2; H, 5.8; N, 8.1; Ni, 6.0%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$, 1644, $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$, 1297, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1620, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ 2921; UV-Vis, λ_{max} (nm), $[\epsilon_{\text{max}} (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1})]$ (acetonitrile), 610 (145), 365 (1159).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) was performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra in KBr (4500–500 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in acetonitrile (1200–350 nm) were recorded in a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. The magnetic

susceptibility measurements were done with an EG & PAR vibrating sample magnetometer, model 155 at room temperature and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants.

Crystal data collection and refinement :

Single crystals having suitable dimensions for complex 1 were used for data collection using a 'Bruker SMART APEX II' diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 150(2) K. The molecular structures were solved by direct methods and refinement by full-matrix least squares on F^2 using the SHELX-97 package¹⁸. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. Hydrogen atoms were placed in their geometrically idealized positions and constrained to ride on their parent atoms. H atoms of water molecules were located by difference Fourier maps and were kept fixed. Programs used are PLATON, ORTEP and MERCURY¹⁹. Crystallographic data for the complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and refinement details of complexes 1 and 2

Complex	1	2
Formula	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{NiO}_2\text{S}$	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{42}\text{Cu}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_8$
Formula weight	366.11	713.78
Temperature (K)	293	293
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$	$C2$
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.886(4)	18.846(2)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.411(5)	10.954(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	32.907(10)	10.632(1)
β (deg)	90.183(7)	119.837(8)
<i>Z</i>	16	2
d_{calc} (g cm^{-3})	1.381	1.245
μ (mm^{-1})	1.230	1.163
<i>F</i> (000)	3072	744
Total reflections	49895	12188
Unique reflections	17340	2305
Observed data [$I > 2 \sigma(I)$]	6485	1577
No. of parameters	806	202
<i>R</i> (int)	0.104	0.079
<i>R</i> 1, <i>wR</i> 2 (all data)	0.1860, 0.1567	0.0939, 0.2189
<i>R</i> 1, <i>wR</i> 2 [$I > 2 \sigma(I)$]	0.0790, 0.1370	0.0801, 0.2012

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The tridentate ligand, HL was prepared by the 1 : 1

condensation of the *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine with 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde in methanol following the literature method²⁰. The ligand was then made to react with nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate and stirred with sodium thiocyanate to prepare complex **1**. Complex **2** was produced by refluxing the ligand, HL with copper(II) acetate in presence of potassium oxalate. The formation of complexes **1** and **2** is shown in Scheme 1.

are occupied by the tridentate Schiff base through two nitrogen (amino and imino) atoms and while other one is occupied by de-protonated phenoxo group. The remaining fourth coordination is satisfied by a thiocyanato ligand. Sum of the different angles around the Ni(1), Ni(2), Ni(3) and Ni(4) atoms is 359.99°, 360.01°, 360.10° and 360.00° indicating a regular square-planar geometry around the metal centre. But the distortion may conveniently be mea-

Scheme 1. Synthetic routes to complexes **1** and **2**.

X-Ray crystallographic studies :

Complex [Ni(L)NCS] (1) :

Complex **1** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group $P2_1/c$. A perspective view of the complex with selective atom-numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 1. The structure determination reveals that it consists of four discrete molecules of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NCS})]$ held together by van der Waals forces only with different bond angle and bond distance around the nickel(II) centre. The nickel(II) centre occupies the central position of a regular square planar arrangement. Out of its four coordination sites three positions

are occupied by the *trans* angles that are ideally 180° for a square-planar complex and 109.5° in a tetrahedral complex. The *trans* angles are found to be 178.7(2)° {O(2)-Ni(1)-N(2)}, 177.5(2)° {N(1)-Ni(1)-N(3)}, 178.6(2)° {O(4)-Ni(2)-N(5)}, 178.4(2)° {N(4)-Ni(2)-N(6)}, 178.3(2)° {O(6)-Ni(3)-N(8)}, 175.6(2)° {N(7)-Ni(3)-N(9)}, 179.7(2)° {O(8)-Ni(4)-N(11)} and 178.0(2)° {N(10)-Ni(4)-N(12)}. Here all the *trans* angles are near 180° and they indicate a regular square-planar geometry around the metal centre. In case of one among the four discrete molecules, the Ni-N bond lengths are found to be Ni(1)-N(1) = 1.835(5);

Fig. 1. Perspective view of complex **1**. Only the relevant atoms are labeled.

Ni(1)-N(2) = 1.973(4); Ni(1)-N(3) = 1.875(6) Å while the Ni(1)-O(2) bond length is 1.836(4) Å. The thiocyanate group, which acts as a monodentate ligand is slightly asymmetric {N(3)-C(15) = 1.153(3) and C(15)-S(1) = 1.635(3) Å}. The other bond lengths and angles are shown in Table 2. The bond lengths and bond angles determined from X-ray measurements are in agreement with the other similar reported systems. The five membered ring, Ni(1)-N(1)-C(9)-C(10)-N(2) has an envelope conformation²¹ on C(10) with puckering parameters²² Q(2) = 0.403(6) Å and $\phi(2) = 102.7(6)^\circ$. The thiocyanate is almost linearly coordinated {Ni(1)-N(3)-C(15) : $167.10(4)^\circ$ and S(1)-C(15)-N(3) : $178.46(4)^\circ$ } as is usual for its N coordination mode. Complex **1** contains C-H... π interactions in the solid-state structure that contribute to the self assembly process. The phenyl ring, Cg(6), present in the molecule {Cg(6) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(17)-C(18)-C(19)-C(20)-C(21)-C(22)]} shows two separate C-H... π interactions, one with symmetry related C(phenyl)-H group of C(3) and another with C(methylene)-H group of C(54). Cg(9) {Cg(9) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(32)-C(33)-C(34)-C(35)-C(36)-C(37)]} forms the third C-H... π interaction with H(11B) and the fourth one is formed between Cg(12) {Cg(12) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(47)-C(48)-C(49)-C(50)-C(51)-C(52)]} and H(26A). Lastly Cg(3) forms another C-H... π interaction with H(49) of a symmetry related molecule. These C-H... π interactions lead to the formation of one dimensional supramo-

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) in [Ni(L)(NCS)] (**1**)

Ni(1)-O(2)	1.836(4)	Ni(3)-O(6)	1.829(4)
Ni(1)-N(1)	1.835(5)	Ni(3)-N(7)	1.850(5)
Ni(1)-N(2)	1.973(4)	Ni(3)-N(9)	1.860(6)
Ni(1)-N(3)	1.875(6)	Ni(3)-N(8)	1.956(6)
Ni(2)-O(4)	1.857(4)	Ni(4)-N(11)	1.964(5)
Ni(2)-N(4)	1.856(5)	Ni(4)-N(12)	1.854(5)
Ni(2)-N(5)	1.987(6)	Ni(4)-N(10)	1.852(5)
Ni(2)-N(6)	1.898(6)	Ni(4)-O(8)	1.834(4)
O(2)-Ni(1)-N(1)	94.1(2)	N(8)-Ni(3)-N(9)	93.4(2)
O(2)-Ni(1)-N(2)	178.7(2)	N(7)-Ni(3)-N(9)	175.6(2)
O(2)-Ni(1)-N(3)	88.2(2)	O(6)-Ni(3)-N(7)	93.8(2)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2)	86.86(19)	O(6)-Ni(3)-N(9)	87.6(2)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(3)	177.5(2)	N(7)-Ni(3)-N(8)	85.3(2)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(3)	90.9(2)	O(8)-Ni(4)-N(10)	93.6(2)
N(4)-Ni(2)-N(5)	87.5(2)	O(8)-Ni(4)-N(12)	88.0(2)
N(4)-Ni(2)-N(6)	178.4(2)	N(10)-Ni(4)-N(11)	86.7(2)
N(5)-Ni(2)-N(6)	91.2(2)	N(10)-Ni(4)-N(12)	178.0(2)
O(4)-Ni(2)-N(5)	178.6(2)	N(11)-Ni(4)-N(12)	91.8(2)
O(4)-Ni(2)-N(4)	93.6(2)	O(8)-Ni(4)-N(11)	179.7(2)

lecular architecture (Fig. 2). Geometric features of the C-H... π interactions are given in Table 3.

Complex [LCu(μ_2 -C₂O₄)CuL] (**2**) :

Complex **2** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group C2. A perspective view of the complex is shown in Fig. 3 and selected bond lengths and angles are listed in Table 4. The complex is centrosymmetric with a non-planar oxalato bridge. Each copper(II) atom is coordinated with one O atom and two N atoms from the ligand L and two O atoms from the oxalate dianion. The distortions of the coordination polyhedron from the square pyramid to the trigonal bipyramid have been calculated by the Addison parameter (τ)²³ as an index of the degree of trigonality. The value of τ is defined as the difference between the two largest donor-metal-donor angles divided by 60, a value that is 0 for the ideal square pyramid and 1 for the trigonal bipyramid. The τ value is 0.02²³. The coordination geometry about the five-coordinate copper(II) ions is thus best described as a square pyramid. The phenolate oxygen atom O(2), the imine nitrogen atoms N(1) and N(2) of ligand, and the oxygen atom O(3) of the oxalato dianion comprise the basal plane, and the another oxalato oxygen atom O(4) is in the apical position. However, the deviation of the basal atoms N(1), N(2), O(2)

Fig. 2. One dimensional supramolecular chain structure of complex **1** generated through the C–H... π interactions.

Table 3. Geometric features (distances in Å and angles in degrees) of the C–H... π interactions obtained for complex **1**

Complex	C–H...Cg(Ring)	H...Cg (Å)	C–H...Cg (°)	C...Cg (Å)	Symmetry
1	C(3)–H(3)...Cg(6)	2.81	153	3.662(6)	x,y,z
	C(11)–H(11B)...Cg(9)	2.80	150	3.673(7)	-x,1/2+y,1/2-z
	C(26)–H(26A)...Cg(12)	3.00	165	3.946(10)	-x,1/2+y,1/2-z
	C(49)–H(49)...Cg(3)	2.82	151	3.661(7)	-x,-1/2+y,1/2-z
	C(54)–H(54A)...Cg(6)	2.82	156	3.727(7)	1-x,-1/2+y,1/2-z

For complex **1**, Cg(3) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(2)–C(3)–C(4)–C(5)–C(6)–C(7)]; Cg(6) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(17)–C(18)–C(19)–C(20)–C(21)–C(22)]; Cg(9) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(32)–C(33)–C(34)–C(35)–C(36)–C(37)] and Cg(12) = Centre of gravity of ring [C(47)–C(48)–C(49)–C(50)–C(51)–C(52)].

Fig. 3. Perspective view of complex **2**. Only the relevant atoms are labeled.

Table 4. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) in [LCu(μ_2 -C₂O₄)CuL] (**2**)

Cu(1)–O(2)	2.088(7)	O(2)–Cu(1)–O(3)	116.8(2)
Cu(1)–O(3)	2.007(6)	O(2)–Cu(1)–O(4)	95.0(2)
Cu(1)–O(4)	2.209(6)	O(2)–Cu(1)–N(1)	88.6(4)
Cu(1)–N(1)	1.879(8)	O(2)–Cu(1)–N(2)	154.6(3)
Cu(1)–N(2)	1.926(7)	O(3)–Cu(1)–O(4)	67.9(2)
O(3)–Cu(1)–N(1)	153.3(3)	O(3)–Cu(1)–N(2)	70.3(3)
O(4)–Cu(1)–N(2)	109.9(3)	N(1)–Cu(1)–N(2)	90.4(4)

and O(3) from their mean plane are 0.328 Å, –0.401 Å, –0.240 Å and 0.313 Å; Cu lies 0.111 Å out of this plane, towards N(1). The intra-molecular distance between the two Cu ions is 5.495 Å, and the closest intermolecular distances between copper ions are 7.277 and 9.532 Å.

IR and electronic spectra :

Strong bands in the range 1630–1580 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of **1** and **2** are attributable to the azomethine group²⁴. The bands at 2921 cm⁻¹ for both the complexes

are due to alkyl C–H bonds. The sharp single ν_{as} band for the N bonded thiocyanate group appears around 2110 cm^{-1} for complex **1**. Similar characteristic bands for thiocyanates have been observed in a number of mononuclear and thiocyanate bridged polynuclear complexes²⁵. Band due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ of the oxalate group appears at 1625 cm^{-1} , respectively in IR spectrum of **2**. The band around 1391 cm^{-1} is attributable to $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$.

The electronic spectra show that absorption bands of complex **1** occur below 600 nm. A lack of any electronic transition at longer wavelengths indicates a large crystal-field splitting and is consistent with the square planar geometry of nickel(II) complexes²⁶. In the electronic spectrum of complex **2** (acetonitrile solution), a relatively weak band appears at around 610 nm, assigned as a *d-d* transition while a broad intense band centered around 365 nm is due to ligand to metal charge transfer.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements showed that the complex **1** is diamagnetic as expected for square planar nickel(II)²⁶.

Summary

The whole work can be concluded in two statements. Firstly, the use of tridentate Schiff base with two ethyl groups on a N atom of the diamine moiety can regulate the electronic and steric demands which could effectively force the formation of mononuclear compound **1**, even in the presence of potential bridging ligand thiocyanate, probably due to the larger size of sulphur. Secondly, the crystal structure of the complex **2** unambiguously shows that the oxalate ion in di- $\mu(\text{O},\text{O}')$ mode can be used for the formation of dinuclear copper(II) complex. The facile synthesis of complex **2** would, therefore, afford a convenient synthetic route for this type carboxylate bridged complexes.

Supplementary data

CCDC 818942 and 928071 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for **1** and **2** respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html> or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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